

www.bjisrd.com

**"MATHEMATICAL STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF THE ORGANIZATION OF
EXPERIMENTAL WORKS AND ITS CONDUCT"**

Scientific supervisor: teacher of SIES

Usanov Kamoliddin Kholboevich

Student of SIES: Khamidova Pokiza Mansurovna

Annotation: This article is about the mathematical statistical analysis of the organization and conduct of experimental tests, the stages, tasks and mathematical statistics of this process have been described

Key words: Experiment-test, experiment-test tasks, mathematical statistics, the subject of mathematical statistics, theoretical basis, probability distribution, statistical research; statistical method; statistical analysis; statistical data.

Introduction: Experimental testing is the process of testing the innovation (methodology, approach, educational-methodical complexes) introduced into a field and obtaining preliminary conclusions. According to the preliminary conclusions, this innovation (methodology, approach, educational -methodical complexes) will be decided on whether to introduce or not.

Experiment-test tasks: experiment-test, sequence, tasks, program, analysis. Due to the fact that experimental work usually lasts for a long time, it is carried out by dividing it into certain stages.

Sequence. It is possible to conduct trial-testing at separate stages of the experiment (at the level of the Republic, region or city and district, inter-school, school level).

Duties. All stages of experimental work (long-term, covering several topics, quarter, academic year, several years depending on the size of the educational materials) and experimental work determine their specific goals and tasks.

Program. First of all, the program of pilot-testing works should be developed, the plan of activities related to pilot-testing, expected results, methods of determining the level of achievement should be reflected in it.

Mathematical statistics is a science that studies methods of collecting statistical data, systematizing them, processing them, and drawing scientific and practical conclusions from them. Mathematical statistics is the main branch of the science of statistics. Statistical theorists study and improve statistical procedures with mathematics, and statistical research often raises mathematical questions. Statistical data means information about the number of elements of sets with certain characteristics. A statistical method is a method of drawing one or another conclusion based on statistical information about specific characteristics of a set of elements. This method is widely used in many fields of science. General characteristics of the application of the statistical method in various fields (counting the elements belonging to a group, finding the distribution of quantitative signs, using the method of equations, finding the number of experiments necessary to reach a conclusion using the theory of probabilities, determining the connections between quantitative signs, etc.) , i.e., the problems in which the nature of the studied objects is insignificant, constitute the prerequisite of mathematical statistics. Since the statistical method is a method of studying mass classification phenomena in most cases, the theory of probabilities forms the theoretical basis of this method. Mathematical statistics consists of descriptive statistics, estimation of unknown parameters, verification of statistical hypotheses, determination of statistical relationships of quantitative signs and other departments.

Statistical data collection is related to research design, especially the design of randomized experiments and the design of surveys using random sampling. Initial data analysis often follows a study protocol established before the study is conducted. Research data can also be analyzed to examine secondary hypotheses inspired by initial results or to suggest new research. Secondary data analysis of planned research uses data analysis tools and the process of doing this is mathematical statistics.

Below are important topics of mathematical statistics.

Probability distribution. A probability distribution is a function that assigns a probability to each measurable subset of the possible outcomes of a random experiment, survey, or statistical inference process. Examples are found in experiments where the sample space is not numerical, where the distribution is a categorical distribution; experiments where the sample space is encoded by discrete random variables, where the distribution can be defined by a probability mass function, and experiments with sample spaces encoded by continuous random variables, where the distribution can be defined by a probability density function. More complex experiments involving stochastic processes defined in continuous time may require the use of more general probability measures.

Mathematical statistical analysis of the organization and conduct of experiments is important in scientific research and problem solving. This process can be divided into stages:

1. Experimental Design

- Data set: Selection of variables and determination of their relationships.
- Randomization: The random allocation of test conditions protects the results from inaccuracies.

- Blocking: Grouping trials under the same conditions to reduce heterogeneity.

2. Testing

- Experimentation: applying specific treatments to each group under specific conditions.
- Collection of results: Systematic recording of the obtained data.

3. Statistical analysis

- Descriptive statistics: Calculation of key indicators such as mean, median, variance and standard deviation.
- Inferential statistics: Analyze the obtained results to generalize and identify doubts, for example: t-test, ANOVA, chi-square test, etc.

4. Interpretation of results

- Drawing conclusions: solving problems or supporting scientific theories based on the obtained results.
- Practical significance of results: Application of acquired knowledge in practice, consideration of possibilities.

5. Report preparation

- Presentation of results: Present data clearly and comprehensibly using graphics, tables and charts.

Final report: Preparation of a document analyzing the learning process and results.

Each of these processes plays an important role in ensuring the effectiveness and scientific significance of experimental work. Data obtained through experiments and their statistical analysis help to develop new theories and expand existing knowledge.

Mathematicians and statisticians such as Gauss, Laplace, and C.S. Peirce used decision theory with probability distributions and loss functions (or utility functions). The decision-theoretic approach to statistical inference was revived by Abraham Wald's successors and made extensive use of scientific computing, analysis, and optimization. Statisticians use algebra and combinatorics to design experiments. But while statistical practice often relies on probability and decision theory, their application can be controversial.

LITERATURE USED:

1. Borovkov, A. A. (1999). *Mathematical Statistics*. CRC Press. ISBN 90-5699-018-7

2. Bickel, Peter J.; Doksum, Kjell A. (2001). *Mathematical Statistics: Basic and Selected Topics*. Vol. 1 (Second (updated printing 2007) ed.). Pearson Prentice-Hall.

3. Hogg, R. V., A. Craig, and J. W. McKean. "Intro to Mathematical Statistics." (2005).

4.Kannan, D.; Lakshmikantham, V., eds. (2002). *Handbook of stochastic analysis and applications*. New York: M. Dekker. ISBN 0824706609.

5.Larsen, Richard J. and Marx, Morris L. "An Introduction to Mathematical Statistics and Its Applications" (2012). Prentice Hall.

6.Schervish, Mark J. (1995). *Theory of statistics (Corr. 2nd print. ed.)*. New York.

7.Virtual Laboratories in Probability and Statistics (Univ. of Ala.-Huntsville)

StatiBot, interactive online expert system on statistical tests.